

Modular Compute Continuum Modelling

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The increasing demand for high data rates, massive data volumes, and guaranteed Quality of Experience (QoE) is driving the need for more advanced communication architectures. Edge computing, which distributes computing capacity from the cloud to locations closer to users, is necessary to address these challenges. This approach combines cloud scalability with energy efficiency and reduced latency [1]. Global spending on edge computing is projected to reach \$232 billion in 2024 and could approach \$350 billion by 2027 [2]. Moreover, the European Union aims to deploy 10000 climate-neutral, highly secure edge nodes by 2030 [3], highlighting the importance of optimizing multi-service and multi-tier edge-cloud infrastructure.

The Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT) of XGain project provides a modular multi-tier compute continuum (CC) modelling (part of Technology Mix Finder & Dimensioning Solver (TMFDS)) where end devices (e.g. drones) have multiple services (e.g. image analysis) and need to be satisfied by various processing devices belonging to different tiers in CC. This modelling identifies infrastructure technology mixes that meet KFT’s user-defined requirements for radio communication and computing devices targeting to an optimal multi-service and multi-tier edge-cloud infrastructure.

Figure 1 Technology Mix Finder & Dimensioning Solver Mechanism

The general architecture of TMFDS process is presented in Fig.1. The information from end user through specific questions and the network and processing databases of KFT are combined to find the appropriate networks and processing technologies in the hierarchical 4-tier deployment model, inspired by [4], shown in the ‘Output’ block. The TMFDS mechanism evaluates about 50 network and computing advanced technologies, based on a detailed stocktaking from scientific literature, market vendors, and expert insights from the consortium. This information (included in KFT’s databases) is used to identify suitable technology combinations, filter potential networks, and calculate the communication components to meet demand.

Moreover, the modular 4-tier design supports diverse user scenarios by accommodating the network technologies between the tiers and the type and number of processing devices in each tier ('Processing Modelling' block). The 'Processing Modelling' element includes the solution of a binary integer non-linear programming (BINLP) optimization problem subject to service latency requirements. In terms of multi-tier design, the 1st tier is the extreme edge, with end devices like drones, while the far edge (2nd tier) is located at radio communication nodes like 5G base stations. The 3rd tier is the near edge, a central point within the service area, and the final tier is the cloud, physically distant from the service deployment. The first three tiers are part of the 'private' infrastructure, while the cloud node is 'public' utilizing cloud providers. Communication between these tiers is managed through a series of hops called as Access, Local and Internet using both wired (e.g., fiber) and wireless networks (e.g., cellular, non-cellular, Internet of Thing (IoT), and satellite). Considering the processing part, a wide range of processing devices with varying capacities, from lightweight devices like Raspberry Pis and NVIDIA single-board computers to more powerful NUCs and rack-mounted servers, with or without GPUs are included in the analysis. Finally, based on the scenarios' characteristics, tiers and communication hops can be added or excluded, confirming the modularity of system's modelling.

In conclusion, the general architecture and modular 4-tier deployment model of the Technology Mix Finder and Dimensioning Solver (part of XGain's KFT) provides a flexible and efficient compute continuum framework for addressing diverse user scenarios. By integrating information from end-user inputs with the extensive network and processing databases of KFT, a wide range of advanced technologies is investigated to identify appropriate combinations of communication networks and processing devices to meet services' latency requirements. Simultaneously the capacities of various processing devices are considered. The ability to add or exclude tiers and communication hops based on scenario-specific needs highlights the practicality and versatility of the architecture's design. This design aims to an optimal compute continuum deployment, which is of utmost importance today.

References

- [1] M. Jansen, et al., "Continuum: Automate infrastructure deployment and benchmarking in the compute continuum," in Companion of the 2023 ACM/SPEC International Conference on Performance Engineering, ICPE '23 Companion, (New York, NY, USA), p. 181–188, Association for Computing Machinery, 2023.
- [2] IDC, "New idc spending guide forecasts edge computing investments will reach \$232 billion in 2024," <https://www.idc.com/getdoc.jsp?containerId=prUS51960324>.
- [3] EU, "2023 report on the state of the digital decade," <https://digital.strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/2023-report-state-digital-decade>.
- [4] L., Tong, Y., Li, and W., Gao, "A hierarchical edge cloud architecture for mobile computing." IEEE INFOCOM 2016-The 35th Annual IEEE International Conference on Computer Communications. pp. 1-9, 2016.

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